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Deliverable 7

Inter-laboratory comparison (ILC) report on the validity and applicability of the developed characterisation methods and reference materials

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	4
General introduction	6
PART I - Cross-comparison of SMP/NP neat materials characterization within the Plastic Trace consortium .7	
1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. MATERIAL AND METHODS	7
2.1. Materials description	7
2.2. Production process of tablets, measurement techniques and relative measurands	8
2.3. TGA	8
2.4. TED-GC/MS	9
2.5. Py-GC/MS (direct analysis)	9
2.6. Py-GC/MS (analysis via derivatization)	9
2.7. FTIR microscopy	10
2.8. Raman microscopy	10
2.9. SEM	10
2.10. Laser diffraction	11
2.11. ATR-FTIR	11
2.12. Quality assurance/quality control	11
3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	11
3.1. Comparison of mass-based thermo-analytical methods	11
3.2. Comparison of micro-spectroscopic methods	13
3.3. Comparison of size characterization methods	17
4. CONCLUSION	17
PART II - An interlaboratory comparison on candidate reference materials to support the standardisation of nanoplastic analysis.....	19
1. INTRODUCTION	19
2. TIMETABLE AND REPORTING	19
3. DELIVERABLES AND DISSEMINATION	19
4. INFORMATION ON TEST MATERIALS SAMPLES, HANDLING AND STORAGE	20
4.1. Material homogeneity and stability	20
4.2. Handling and storage	20
5. TECHNIQUES AND MEASURANDS	20
6. DLS/MADLS PROTOCOL	21
6.1. Sample Handling	21
6.2. Measurement protocol	21
6.3. Data analysis	22
6.4. Further reading	22
7. FFF-MALS PROTOCOL	23
7.1. Overview	23
7.2. Instrumentation	24
7.3. Mobile Phase Preparation	24
7.4. Experimental Plan and Analysis Procedure	24
7.5. Data treatment and reporting	26
7.6. Further reading	27
8. PTA PROTOCOL	27
8.1. Sample Handling	27
8.2. Measurement protocol	27
8.3. Data analysis	28
8.4. Further reading	28
9. THERMOANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES PROTOCOL	29

9.1	Sample preparation.....	29
9.2	Instrumental conditions	29
9.3	Calibration and quantification	29
10.	PRELIMINARY FINDINGS OF VAMAS TWA 45, PROJECT 3.....	30
10.1	Measuring size distribution by DLS/MADLS methods	30
10.3	Measuring number concentration by PTA method.....	33
10.4	Measuring mass fraction by thermoanalytical methods	34
11.	CONCLUSIONS.....	35
12.	ANNEX I.....	36
13.	ANNEX II.....	46

Executive Summary

The Plastic Trace project addresses the urgent need for harmonised methods to characterise small microplastics (SMPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) in support of new EU regulations. Candidate SMPs reference materials produced in the frame of the project were characterised by the partners of the consortium using thermo-analytical, spectroscopic, and size-distribution techniques. Results showed strong inter-technique comparability and material suitability for method validation. In parallel, the VAMAS TWA 45 Project 3 interlaboratory comparison engaged international laboratories to assess repeatability and reproducibility of targeted methods for NPs characterisation. These efforts provide a foundation for best-practice guidance, harmonisation, and future ISO standards.

GLOSSARY/ABBREVIATIONS

DLS: Dynamic Light Scattering

ILC: Inter-Laboratory Comparison

μ -FTIR: Micro Fourier–Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

μ -Raman: Micro Raman Spectroscopy

FFF: Field Flow Fractionation

MADLS: Multiangle Dynamic Light Scattering

MALS: Multiangle Light Scattering

NPLs: Nanoplastics

PTA: Particle Tracking Analysis

Py-GC/MS: Pyrolysis coupled with Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry

QCM: Quality Control Material

RM: Reference Material

SEM: Scanning Electron Microscopy

SMPs: small microplastics TED-GC/MS: Thermal Extraction and Desorption GC/MS

UV-Vis: Ultraviolet-Visible

VAMAS: Versailles project on advanced materials and standards

General introduction

Interlaboratory comparisons (ILCs) play a central role in standardising methodologies for the characterisation of small microplastics (SMPs) and nanoplastics (NPLs). They strengthen research consistency by identifying best practices and areas for improvement, thereby ensuring reproducibility and reliability of results across laboratories.

Within the Plastic Trace project, LNE, BAM, INRIM, LGC, and NIVA jointly defined a strategy for ILCs on selected SMP/NP neat materials. Insights gained from the production and characterisation of these materials — including homogeneity and stability testing using a range of analytical techniques — guided the decision to focus on three key measurands: particle number concentration, mass fraction, and particle size.

This report is divided into two parts. **Part I** presents work on the development and characterisation of candidate reference materials for microplastics. Tablets containing polyethylene terephthalate (PET) particles (10–100 μm , irregular and sharp-edged) were produced at three concentration levels. A broad suite of techniques was applied to assess particle size, morphology, polymer type, homogeneity, and stability, including mass-based methods (TGA, Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS), spectroscopic methods (μ -FTIR, μ -Raman), and size distribution approaches (SEM, laser diffraction). Results obtained across different instruments, laboratories, and analytical principles demonstrated strong inter-technique comparability, supporting the suitability of the PET tablets as reference materials for method validation and harmonisation.

Part II presents a key achievement of the project: the organisation of the VAMAS TWA 45 Project 3 ILC. This international study focused on validating targeted techniques for measuring nanoplastics in terms of size distribution, number concentration, and mass fraction. By involving multiple laboratories worldwide, the ILC provides critical data for assessing method repeatability and reproducibility, supporting harmonisation and pre-standardisation.

Together, these efforts contribute directly to method harmonisation and best-practice guidance, paving the way for the validated techniques to be widely implemented in regulatory and industrial applications. Ultimately, they represent a crucial step towards improving the comparability of SMP/NP measurements and towards the development of new environmental and food safety standards.

PART I - Cross-comparison of SMP/NP neat materials characterization within the Plastic Trace consortium

*The work presented in this report is extracted from a broader study performed in the Plastic Trace project on the production and characterization of candidate reference materials, which has been submitted for publication. The entire publication manuscript is attached in **Annex 1**. The focus here is to highlight the comparability of different techniques, instruments, and partner contributions within that larger framework.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Growing concern over the risks of microplastics (MPs, 1–1000 μm) has led the EU to introduce mandatory monitoring in directives such as the Drinking Water Directive and Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive. Effective regulation requires standardized, validated methods for sampling, preparation, and detection, supported by well-characterized reference materials. Currently, the spectroscopy methods micro Fourier–transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR) and micro Raman spectroscopy (μ -Raman) are widely used for particle identification and counting, while the thermo-analytical methods pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) and thermal extraction desorption-GC-MS (TED-GC/MS) are applied for mass quantification. However, suitable MP reference materials must closely resemble environmental MPs — mainly irregular fragments in the 10–100 μm size range — and be available in concentrations reflecting different real-world contexts (e.g., wastewater, food). Producing such materials is challenging due to their very low masses, but embedding MPs with tableting can ensure quantitative handling and distribution.

In Plastic Trace project reference materials to support MP regulation and harmonization have been created. Using a quality-by-design approach, tablets containing polyethylene terephthalate (PET) MPs (10–100 μm , irregular, sharp-edged) were produced at three concentration levels:

1. environmental-like concentration for mass-based thermos-analytical methods
2. food-related concentration detectable for both mass- and number-based analysis methods
3. very low mass approaching the limit of reporting (LOR) for number-based spectroscopic methods

MPs were characterized for size, shape, and polymer type, and homogeneity/stability was verified using thermogravimetric analysis, μ -FTIR, and μ -Raman, following ISO Guide 30 and ISO 33405:2024. Complete description of the material production process, quality by design approach, homogeneity, and stability control studies can be found in **Annex1**.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Materials description

Directly compressible lactose (FlowLac90, D50: 138.2 +/- 3.1 μm) was provided by MEGGLE GmbH & Co. KG and used as the tablet matrix. Polyethylene glycol 6000 (PEG, D50: 98.5 +/- 2.2 μm) was purchased at Merck. PET powder was provided by BAM with a irregular particle shape and a broad size distribution (from 5 to 500 μm , D50: 42.4 +/- 0.2 μm). Low-density polyethylene (LDPE), most probably produced by polymer emulsion, was kindly provided by Schaeetti AG, Wallisellen, Switzerland (D50: 18.0 +/- 0.7 μm). The particle size distribution measurements were determined by laser diffraction in dry dispersion (Instrumental equipment: HELOS/BR+RHODOS/L+ASPIROS) with a mass of 100 mg.

2.2. Production process of tablets, measurement techniques and relative measurands

The MP particles (starting material) were characterized for size and shape with laser diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), while polymer verification was conducted by FTIR. To produce a viable reference material for the mass-based method concentrations, homogeneity and stability control assessment was completed with at least 10 individual tablets using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) according to ISO Guide 30 and ISO 33405:2024. The tablets containing the lowest PET MP concentration was checked for homogeneity and stability with μ -FTIR and μ -Raman. The full scheme of analysis are showed in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1. Production process and characterization methods used for the different batches (Batch 1: B1, Batch 2: B2, Batch 3: B3) of tablets containing the different PET MP concentrations and for Blanks containing the tablet matrix only.

Table 1. Measurement techniques and relative measurands

	Measurand	Methods
Homogeneity and stability control (monitored parameter)	Mass fraction	TGA
Characterized concentration values	Particle number	μ -FTIR, μ -Raman
	Mass fraction	Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS
Identification and dimensional characterization	Size and size distribution	Laser diffraction
	Shape	SEM
	Polymer type	FTIR

2.3. TGA

For thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), the sample was heated up to 600 °C under inert atmosphere (N₂, 30 mL) with 10 K/min. The instrument is provided from Mettler-Toledo (TGA/DSC 3+, Mettler Toledo, USA). The mass loss was measured, and the decomposition temperature of the compounds were determined.

2.4. TED-GC/MS

ThermoExtractionDesorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC/MS) is a multi-step instrument coupling between TGA (TGA/DSC 3+, Mettler Toledo, USA) and GC/MS (7890 B und 5977 B MSD, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA). The sample is heated from 25 to 600°C under N₂ atmosphere. The decomposition gases are collected on a solid phase adsorber. After the extraction step is finished the adsorber has been fully automatically transported to the GC/MS system, where the gases are released from the adsorber by smart heating to 200°C, collected with a cold injection system at -100°C, before going through the GC column for separation and mass detection in MS. The samples were measured directly after filtration and drying.

2.5. Py-GC/MS (direct analysis)

The PET particles from the tablets were isolated by filtration using a stainless-steel filter holder with a Whatman glass fiber filter (13 mm filter size, 1.6 µm pore size) and a 20 ml glass syringe connected to a VisiprepTM vacuum manifold (Supelco Sigma-Aldrich Co.). Tablets (blind and PET) were placed into the syringe barrel, and Milli-Q water was added until the barrel was filled halfway and left to stand for 4 minutes to ensure complete dissolution of the tablet. The sample was rinsed several times by adding different volumes of Milli-Q water, totaling 150 ml, to guarantee the dissolution of the matrix. The filter was folded and placed in the pyrolysis ECO-cup (80µl, Frontier Labs) and dried in an oven at 40°C for a minimum of 4 hours. Blind tablets were prepared in the same way. Samples were placed directly into the pyrolyser. Analysis was performed using a Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) (Frontier Labs, Japan) coupled with an Agilent 8860 GC and an Agilent 5977A MSD (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer operated in single-shot mode with pyrolysis at 600 °C for 0.5 min. The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were set to 300 °C, and the split ratio was 100:1. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved using a HP-5MS UI capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 µm film thickness, and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed to start at 40°C for 2 min, then increased at a rate of 20°C/min up to 325°C (14 min), followed by an increase of 30°C up to 340°C. The transfer line temperature was maintained at 320 °C, the ion source temperature at 280 °C, and the quadrupole temperature at 150 °C. The ion source operated in Full Scan mode. PET was quantified using Benzoic acid as marker (*m/z* 77;105;122) and Biphenyl (*m/z* 154), Benzene (*m/z* 78) and Vinyl benzoate (*m/z* 51;77;105) as confirmation markers, using external calibration.

2.6. Py-GC/MS (analysis via derivatization)

Tablets (blind and PET) were placed to 40 mL glass vials and 20 mL of MilliQ-water added. The samples were then placed in a sonication bath until complete dissolution of the tablet was achieved. The PET particles were isolated from the solution using a 5 µm stainless steel filter, and the filter then transferred to a glass vial to dry gently at 40 °C. Once dry, enough DCM/TFA 2:1 (trifluoroacetic acid/dichloromethane) solution to fully cover the filter (<5 mL) was added and the samples placed in an ultrasonication bath (room temperature) for 10 minutes. The resulting extract was transferred to a 10 mL volumetric flask. The extraction of the filter was repeated, the two extracts combined, and the volume adjusted to 10 mL. A subsample the extract of known volume was then transferred to a pyrolysis crucible and evaporated first at 40 °C for 10 min to remove the DCM, and then at 60 °C for 30 min until dry. Next, 10 µL of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH; 25% in MeOH) was added to the pyrolysis crucible and evaporated at 60 °C, until dry. Blank samples were prepared in the same way, but without blind or PET-containing tablets. Analysis was performed using a Frontier Multi-Shot Pyrolyzer (PY-3030D) coupled to an Agilent 7890A GC with an Agilent 5975C MS (Py-GC/MS) (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The pyrolyzer was operated in single-shot mode with pyrolysis at 600 °C (1.0 min). The pyrolyzer interface and GC inlet temperatures were 320 °C, and the split ratio was 25:1. The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow of 1 mL/min. Separation was achieved using a HP5-MS UI capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 µm film thickness, and 0.25 mm internal diameter). The column oven temperature was programmed at 40 °C (2 min) and ramped up by 20 °C/min until it reached 320 °C (25 min hold). The transfer line temperature was 320 °C, the ion source temperature was 230 °C, and the quadrupole temperature was 150 °C. A solvent delay of 2 minutes was used to avoid derivatization byproducts on the mass

spectrometer. The ion source was operated in SIM mode with quantification of PET via derivatization product dimethyl terephthalate (approximately 11.3 minutes retention time) using m/z 163 (quantifier) and 194 (qualifier).

2.7. FTIR microscopy

Two labs performed μ -FTIR measurements named Lab 1 and Lab 2 which had the same parameters and instrument. The μ -FTIR measurements of PET tablets Batch 2 were conducted using Thermo ScientificTM Nicolet iN10 infrared microscope, equipped with a KBr/Ge beam splitter and a mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) detector. The silicon filters were scanned with a 15x objective (numerical aperture: 0.7; working distance: 16 mm). Spectra were recorded in transmission mode with a spectral range of 4000 – 650 cm^{-1} . The spectral acquisition was done with 16 scans at the resolution of 8 cm^{-1} and an integration time of 3 seconds. The data acquisition, as well as spectral analysis, were performed with OMNIC Picta software. Particles detected were listed in a table with the size fractions to align them with the ISO norm 16094-2.

2.8. Raman microscopy

(Lab1). Raman measurements of Lab1 were done on a LabRAM HR Evolution (HORIBA, France SAS) using a 50x Olympus objective (0.75 NA). The spectrometer was equipped with a 600 g/mm grating and a 532 nm laser (100 mW). To identify the particles, a dark-field light was used to capture the image of the filter which was then analyzed by the Particle Finder software (HORIBA, France SAS). To remove the filter's pore and to discriminate particles, the minimum area (in μm^2) was fixed to 20 μm , two masks (erode 5x5 and dilate 5x5) were applied on the image and the intensity threshold was optimized to get the most efficient segmentation, meaning the most accurate identification of the particle size and chemical identification. Particle analysis was done by setting 0.1 s of acquisition time and 1 accumulation. The chemical identification was done by using an in-house random forest model (Da Costa Filho, Sci Rep, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-03458-7>)

(Lab2). Chemical identification of PET tablets was conducted by using a LabRAM Odyssey Raman spectrometer (HORIBA Scientific) for Lab 2. The filters were scanned with an Olympus 10x objective (numerical aperture: 0.25) with dark field illumination to minimize the contribution of the pores and making the analysis of the image easier. The image was analyzed with the Particle Finder tool integrated in the software LabSpec. Raman spectra of particles were acquired by using a laser with an excitation wavelength of 633 nm, a power of 12 mW, and an exposure time of 1 s for a single accumulation per spectrum. A 1800 l/mm grating was used, and the spectral range 1570-1825 cm^{-1} was considered for this study. The identity of the MPs was confirmed by Horiba ID Finder software comparing with the Horiba Raman spectral database. To achieve identification, a matching score threshold of 60% (HQI) and a dimensional threshold of 7 μm was fixed.

(Lab3). Raman measurements were conducted using commercial Raman Systems (LabRam Soleil from Horiba) for Lab 3. The Raman spectrum of PET has significant Raman signals in the range of 750-3500 cm^{-1} . A 532 nm laser, adjusted to 25% of the power time (ND filter 24 mW) were selected for acquisition. The study employed Particle Finder software acquisition (LabSpec Setup) with 0.2 seconds of acquisition time and accumulation fixed at 2. The images were achieved using 20x LWD objective lens equipped with a dark field microscopy Raman Spectrometer to observe PET-particles. The identity of the MPs was confirmed by comparing Horiba Particle Finder Raman spectral database. Data process provides morphological filters and other tools to improve and enhance the particle segmentation. To achieve identification, a matching score threshold was fixed at 60% (HQI) and a specify minimum particle (min Feret diameter) was fixed at 5 μm corresponding to the pore size where smallest particles will be excluded.

2.9. SEM

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to investigate the Si (Figure S1 left) and the shape of the PET particles. The PET samples were sputtered with an approx. 15 nm thick gold layer. The micrographs were obtained

using an EVO MA 10 scanning electron microscope (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany) with a secondary electron detector and an accelerating voltage of 10 kV.

2.10. Laser diffraction

The size distribution of the PET powder used as polymeric particles in the tablets was measured using laser diffraction in a classic diffraction arrangement with a parallel beam path. The HELOS laser diffraction system from Sympatec GmbH (Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany) is set according to ISO 13320 and is combined with the dry dispersing unit RODOS and the ASPIROS microdosing unit for feeding very small quantities of dry substances. The measurements were carried out in replicates with 10 vials and 3 measurements with per vial with the R5 lens (size range: 4.5 - 875 μm). Mass intake was 100 mg each. Injector-width was set to 4 mm, the pre-pressure to 2.5 bar and the ASPIROS sled velocity was 100 mm/s. The optical concentration resulted in 2.3-5.8%. The diffraction data were analyzed using the parameter-free Fraunhofer model.

2.11. ATR-FTIR

Attenuated total reflectance-FTIR (ATR-FTIR) measurement was done for the PET powder to confirm the polymer type. The PET powder (starting material) was placed on a ZnSe crystal and measured directly with the Nicolet 6700 FT-IR Spectrometer. The instrument is equipped with a DTGS KBr Detector and a Smart ORBIT unit. The spectra is ATR crystal and background corrected. The spectrum is presented in Figure S2 proving the PET polymer type.

2.12. Quality assurance/quality control

All labs followed the ISO 16094-2 and 16094-3 norms regarding quality assurance and quality control, including the management of reagents, taking relevant precautions with laboratory environment, and the use of analytical control blanks. Careful attention was given to ensuring all the reagents used in the sample/filtration process, including the reference water and chemicals (ethanol, surfactant), were pre-filtered before use with a non-polymeric membrane with a pore size $\leq 5 \mu\text{m}$ to remove any contaminant microplastics. The ubiquitous nature of microplastic in the working environment was considered by taking contamination prevention measures, including not wearing gloves, washing hands and washing the outside of all containers. Laboratory personnel wore cotton lab coats and did not wear face masks or cosmetics. Most work was conducted under a laminar flow hood that was regularly cleaned. The use of plastic-based equipment was avoided to prevent cross-contamination.

The establishment of analytical control blanks is mandatory to measure the impact of the different steps (sampling and filtration) and ensure the quality and significance of the analysis is in line with ISO standard 12141:2024. For that purpose, an analytical control blank comprising particle-free water of known quality was produced for each analysis in series. This blank followed the same protocol as the corresponding sample and was analyzed first to ensure that no contamination has been introduced during the sampling and filtration process. This is most important for number-based quantification methods, which detect each individual particle. Although the same blank controls were used for mass-based quantification methods, the mass of any possible contamination is often below the LOD. The number or mass of PET particles found in the blank samples were subtracted from the results of the main samples as part of accurate measurements.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Comparison of mass-based thermo-analytical methods

A total of 17 PET-containing tablets from Batch 1 were each analyzed with Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS with direct sample preparation (PET tablet particles on filters). Further measurements were carried out with 10 tablets that

were analyzed by Py-GC/MS after derivatization of the PET particles (Fig. 2). All 44 measurements of Batch 1 are in good relation to each other, with a mean mass value of 422.3 μg , a mean standard deviation (STD) of 88.7 μg , and a mean relative STD 21.0%. Importantly, this mean PET mass value is fully consistent with the reference value of 398.0 \pm 47.3 μg determined in the homogeneity control by TGA. Direct Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS show quite comparable mean values of 448.9 μg and 431.3 μg , respectively, with both slightly overestimating the mass of PET relative to the TGA reference value. The STD of TED-GC/MS (55.7 μg) is lower than that of Py-GC/MS (105.1 μg). The derivatized PET particles detected by Py-GC/MS gave a slight underestimation compared to the reference value, indicating not all of the PET particles were fully derivatized. Non-derivatized PET will not be detected when using dimethyl terephthalate as the quantifier.

Figure 2: PET masses per tablet detected with direct Py-GC/MS analysis, direct TED-GC/MS analysis, and with derivatization Py-GC/MS analysis. The table gives mean values, STD and relative STD in numbers. The results for Batch 1 PET tablets are presented on the left side of the figure and the results for Batch 2 PET tablets are presented on the right side of the figure.

The concentration of PET particles in the Batch 2 tablets is diluted by a factor of 30 compared to the Batch 1 tablets. This dilution was conducted to achieve a PET concentration that is more realistic according to the microplastic mass/numbers found in food products. For Batch 2, 10 tablets were directly analyzed by Py-GC/MS and 10 tablets were directly analyzed by TED-GC/MS. A further 10 tablets were analyzed by Py-GC/MS using derivatization. All three methods show similar mean values with an average of 17.1 \pm 5.7 μg (33.1%) that corresponds well to the TGA reference value of 19.8 \pm 1.8 μg . The direct and derivatized Py-GC/MS measurements are very similar in mass (17.7 and 16.8 μg) and STD (3.9 and 4.5 μg), while the STD and relative STD of the TED-GC/MS measurements is quite high with values of 8.2 μg and 48.6%, respectively.

The Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS analyses show generally the same masses for both Batch 1 and Batch 2 tablets as those determined by TGA. The higher PET masses present in the Batch 1 tablets are slightly overestimated compared to the TGA, while the smaller PET masses in the Batch 2 tablets, which are near the instrumental LODs, are within the TGA reference value or are slightly underestimated. Overall, the masses and the STDs are in the same range for both batches of PET tablets and correspond well with theoretical values and the TGA reference values. This makes the PET tablets a valuable product for use in method validation for microplastic

identification and quantification methods supporting EU directives and monitoring campaigns to measure true values.

Figure 3. PET masses per tablet determined by mass-based methods for Batch 1 (left) and Batch 2 (right) as stability control assessment; n=2-5 (The red line indicates the theoretical mass).

Stability control of the PET tablets was performed on 2 to 5 tablets after 6 months for Batch 1 and after 12 months for Batch 2 (Fig. 3). No significant changes in mass could be observed, relative to the values determined at month 0, for either batch of tablets using three different techniques: TGA, Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS. On the one hand, the results indicate that the PET tablets are stable over these timeframes; on the other hand, they demonstrate **inter-technique comparability, irrespective of the PET concentration.**

3.2. Comparison of micro-spectroscopic methods

The PET-containing tablets were also analyzed for particle numbers and size distributions as this is an important metric for supplementing the mass, especially as microplastic monitoring typically requires particle number to be reported. The Batch 1 tablets were not analyzed using the spectroscopic techniques as the high concentration of PET particles would result in too many particles being collected on the filters. This has the double challenge of overloading the filters and making it difficult for the image-based techniques to identify and analyze individual particles, while a higher number of particles requires much more time to complete a full analysis of the filter. Therefore, the Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets with a lower theoretical PET particle concentration were analyzed with the spectroscopic techniques.

Figure 4. Lab-to-lab comparison of PET particle numbers per tablet detected by μ -Raman of three different partners for Batch 2.

Three different laboratories measured the Batch 2 tablets to determine the number of PET particles numbers and their respective sizes. One lab analyzed 8 tablets (Lab 2) with μ -Raman, another lab analyzed 10 tablets with μ -Raman (Lab 3), and the final lab analyzed 10 tablets with μ -Raman and μ -FTIR (Lab 1). A comparison of the resulting PET tablet particle numbers, which are counted and sorted for the size fractions 1-5, 5-10, 10-20, 20-50, 50-100 and 100-500 μm , is shown in Fig. 4. In addition, the values are compared to those determined by laser diffraction for the pristine PET particles. The particle numbers in the individual size classes match well within and between the laboratories. The mean total particle number ($n=28$) in the Batch 2 tablets with a size between 20 and 500 μm is 1,764 \pm 155 (8.8%). The sizes correspond well with the results of the laser diffraction.

Table 2. Comparison of integrated areas of distinct size fractions determined with laser diffraction to mean values of all partners of particle numbers per fraction and over all 28 tablets measured.

	Size fraction	μm	5-10	10-20	20-50	50-100	100-500
Laser diffraction	Ratio integrated area	%	0.5	4.4	49.1	44.4	1.7
	Ratio integrated area (mean all labs)	%	9.3	19.0	49.7	18.8	3.2

A direct comparison of the relative number of particles per size class determined by μ -Raman and the integrated area of the size classes determined by laser diffraction shows relatively good agreement (Table 2). Almost 50% of

all particles were in the size range of 20-50 μm . A shift towards detecting a higher proportion of smaller particles could be observed for μ -Raman. It could be evidence that the tableting process is fragmenting the particles leading to an increase in smaller particles and a decrease in the larger particle size fractions. It is also known that laser diffraction can be evaluated according to the Fraunhofer or the MIEE model, which are more suitable for larger or smaller particles. As the size distribution is broad, the Fraunhofer evaluation was used as a compromise, with larger particles being preferred.

While laser diffraction showed that 44% of PET particles were in the size range 50-100 μm , the number of particles counted with μ -Raman in this size class represented only 19%. Furthermore, μ -Raman detected higher proportions of PET particles in the smaller size classes 10-20 and 5-10 μm .

Figure 5. Comparison of particle numbers of Batch 2 (left) and Batch 3 (right) detected with μ -FTIR and μ -Raman, $n=10$, all measurements are done in the same laboratory (Lab 1).

The particle number counted with μ -Raman for Batch 2 were also compared to particle number values determined with μ -FTIR. The particle size detection limit for μ -FTIR is larger than detection limit for μ -Raman. According to ISO/DIS 16094-2, therefore, μ -FTIR analysis was only performed for particles larger than 20 μm . A similar comparison was conducted for the Batch 3 tablets containing the lowest concentration of PET particles. The results are presented in Fig. 5. Although the total number of particles has been reduced from 1759 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) for Batch 2 to 151 particles for Batch 3 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) it is clear that the size distribution is similar. The particle numbers counted with μ -Raman and μ -FTIR for both Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets were similar for particle sizes larger than 50 μm . In contrast, μ -FTIR detects 56% less (Batch 2) and 55% less (Batch 3) PET particles than μ -Raman in the 20-50 μm size category. The similar size distribution independent of the concentration, indicates a systematic measurement error based on different measurement methods.

For the μ -Raman, all size distributions for Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets determined by microscopy show the highest relative standard deviations for smallest and largest size categories (5-10 and 100-500 μm), while the lowest

relative standard deviations were recorded for the size fraction 20-50 μm . This is probably due to the number of particles per size class. From a statistical point of view, it is easier to distribute more particles of the same size homogeneously from tablet to tablet than fewer particles. The presence or absence of individual particles in a tablet changes the relative standard deviation much more when the total number of particles in a size class is very small. For the $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ data the relative standard deviations are notably higher across all measured size categories compared to the equivalent $\mu\text{-Raman}$ values. The highest relative standard deviations for both Batch 2 and Batch 3 are observed for the smallest size category measurable by $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ (20-50 μm). This indicates that particles in this size range, at least those around 20 μm , are at the instrumental limits of detection, as μRaman analysis consistently showed that the 20-50 μm size range contained the highest number of PET particles in all tablets tested. The results clearly demonstrate that $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ can robustly determine PET particle numbers down to a particle size of 50 μm , while $\mu\text{-Raman}$ allows robust identification and quantification of PET particles down to at least 20 μm .

Matrix contamination. Although blank control samples need to be conducted for determination of accurate particle mass and number measurements as part of QA/QC, it is equally important to analyze the matrix (lactose and PEG) as possible source for contamination. Therefore, matrix blank tablets were produced containing lactose and PEG but with no addition of PET particles. These tablets were tested in the participating different laboratories for particle number and mass after running through the entire filtration process in the same way as for the PET-containing tablets. Analysis of the resulting data revealed that no thermoplastic polymers were detected in the matrix material using thermo-analytical methods. This indicates that no thermoplastic particles were present or, more likely, that the mass of any polymer contamination is below the LODs of the instruments.

In contrast to the thermo-analytical analysis of the matrix blank tablets, six different types of polymer particle were detected in the number-based spectroscopic approaches. A summary of the results is provided in Fig. 6. Polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), PET, polyamide (PA) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) particles were found across 8 tablets analyzed by $\mu\text{-Raman}$ and 7 tablets analyzed by $\mu\text{-FTIR}$. For $\mu\text{-Raman}$, 6 of the 8 matrix blank tablets contained polymer particles, ranging in number from 1 particle to 51 particles. PS particles dominate 3 of the tablets (27-32 particles), while PET (1-6 particles) was found in 5 of the matrix blank tablets. For $\mu\text{-FTIR}$, all 7 of the matrix blank tablets contained polymer particles, ranging in number from 2 particles to 36 particles. PET particles were found in 5 of the 7 the matrix blank tablets, ranging from 1-16 particles.

Figure 6. Plastic contamination found in matrix blank tablets as determined by $\mu\text{-Raman}$ and $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ (n=8/n=7).

Overall, the number of contaminant particles detected was very low (>3%) compared to the total mean number of PET particles present in the Batch 2 tablets (1,759 particles). In the case of the Batch 2 tablets, the matrix is considered to be sufficiently clean for it to be used to produce reference materials containing this concentration of PET particles. It should be noted that the number of polymer particles identified by the spectroscopic methods in the matrix blank tablets includes both matrix contamination as well as any possible contamination occurring during the sample production, storage, transportation, sample preparation (filtration) and measurement of the filter itself. When comparing the two analysis techniques, μ -Raman detects more particles than μ -FTIR. This is expected due to the lower particle size detection limit of Raman microscopes and may explain why PS particles were not found in μ -FTIR if they are smaller than 20 μm . PTFE particle contamination was also only be detected by μ -Raman, which indicates that the particles are again <20 μm and that somewhere in the sample preparation process a seal made of PTFE was used. It should also be noted that PS and PTFE contamination was only found in the same 3 tablets analyzed by μ -Raman and not the other 5 tablets, indicating the contamination was not consistent.

3.3. Comparison of size characterization methods

SEM images showed that the pristine PET particles were irregular shaped with sharp edges, and that a range of particle sizes was evident (Fig. 7). Laser diffraction analysis confirmed that the pristine PET particles had a broad size distribution, with distribution density values of $D_{10}=19.1 \pm 0.2$ (1.0%), $D_{50}=42.4 \pm 0.2$ (0.4%) and $D_{90}=72.9 \pm 0.3$ (0.5%), where $D_{10}/D_{50}/D_{90}$ is the equivalent particle diameter of the measured volume below which 10.3/50.3/90.3% of the particles are. It should be noted that 93.5% of all particles are in the size range between 20 and 100 μm with an approximately equal number distributed across the size fractions 20-50 μm (49.1%) and 50-100 μm (44.4%) (Table 2).

Figure 7. SEM image (left) and particle size distribution of PET particles (right).

4. CONCLUSION

Across all three groups of techniques — mass-based thermo-analytical methods, micro-spectroscopic approaches, and size characterization methods — the results demonstrate a high level of inter-technique comparability in both absolute values and trends.

Mass-based techniques (TGA, Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS) consistently delivered PET mass values that were in close agreement with each other and with the theoretical reference values, independent of PET concentration.

Micro-spectroscopic analyses (μ -Raman, μ -FTIR) provided comparable particle number and size distributions across laboratories, with differences largely explained by methodological detection limits. Importantly, the consistency in particle size distribution across Batches 2 and 3 confirmed that concentration did not bias the measurement outcome, although instrument-specific sensitivities (e.g. for particles <20 μm) remain a factor.

Size characterization methods (SEM, laser diffraction) corroborated the irregular morphology and broad distribution of PET particles, while quantifying size ranges that aligned with spectroscopic observations.

Overall, the comparability of results between and within methods, and across independent laboratories, underscores the robustness of the PET tablets as a candidate reference material. Their demonstrated stability, reproducibility, and representativeness make them highly suitable for supporting method validation and harmonization efforts in microplastic monitoring and regulatory frameworks.

PART II - An interlaboratory comparison on candidate reference materials to support the standardisation of nanoplastic analysis

The work presented in the Part II of the report is issued from the VAMAS interlaboratory comparison - project 3 on candidate reference material, to support the standardisation of nanoplastic analysis. This study was conducted under the auspices of VAMAS Technical Working Area 45 and of the EURAMET Plastic Trace Project.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several research needs have been identified by International Organisations as the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA), the Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA), and the World Health Organization (WHO). Among these is the development of representative reference materials for plastic particles across various size ranges. As part of the EURAMET Plastic Trace Project (<https://plastictrace.eu/>), sub-micron plastic particles and nanoplastics, reflective of common industrial polymers, have been produced and characterised. However, standardised measurement protocols and methodologies for the reliable analysis of the physico-chemical properties of nanoplastics are still absent.

The objective of the VAMAS interlaboratory comparison - project 3 is to evaluate the performance of the following targeted techniques to measure the size distribution, number concentration and mass fraction of nanoplastic particles:

- Light Scattering techniques (DLS, MADLS) - size distribution
- Fractionation techniques hyphenated to Static Light Scattering (FFF-MALS) - size distribution
- Particle Tracking Analysis (PTA) - number concentration
- Thermoanalytical techniques (Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS) - mass fraction

Results will support harmonization and pre-standardization, providing data for assessing method repeatability and reproducibility.

This document contains information on the test sample (storage, handling and preparation), the target measurands, the ILC protocols for the selected techniques and preliminary results.

2. TIMETABLE AND REPORTING

Surfactant-free aqueous suspensions of nano-polypropylene test materials were distributed in May 2025 alongside with the protocols. The time required to carry out the measurements may depend on the technique; 1 week is a rough estimate.

A shared online space was set up on the PlasticTrace project SharePoint hosted by NIVA, for collecting the ILC results. Each participant received by email an individual invitation to access this online space where a folder with the organisation acronym is set. When accessing the folder as an external user, the participant can only view the folder assigned and not those of other participants. In the folder participants find the templates for data reporting. All participants were asked to return data and other requested information (e.g., quality control details, technical issues encountered, etc.) using the data reporting templates provided by the study organizers.

3. DELIVERABLES AND DISSEMINATION

The measurement results reported by ILC participants are under process to evaluate consensus values for analysed samples and to assess the precision of the targeted methods. Statistical analysis are based on methodology described

in ISO 5725-2 (repeatability and reproducibility). Data produced in this ILC may contribute to assignment of reference values to the test material. Results from participants will be anonymized in reports and publications. The selected final datasets are planned to be hosted in an open-access repository, such as Zenodo. It is planned to summarize the developed measurement protocols and ILC data in a VAMAS report, then publish in a peer-reviewed journal (Publication with Acknowledgement of all ILC participants). In the best-case scenario these results may contribute to new ISO standards.

4. INFORMATION ON TEST MATERIALS SAMPLES, HANDLING AND STORAGE

4.1. Material homogeneity and stability

In this ILC the nanoplastic representative test material is an irregular shaped nano-polypropylene suspension in water, bottled in vials containing 2 mL each. The material has been produced by the German Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM). Homogeneity and stability monitoring studies on the test material (TM), according to the particle size distribution and the number concentration, have been carried out in the frame of the Plastic Trace project according to ISO 17034 and ISO Guide 35:2017 and proved homogeneous distribution between individual vials and stability over 12 month.

4.2. Handling and storage

All participants received a number of TM vials based on the techniques they were using. No dilution of the TM is required for FFF-MALS. For DLS/MADLS and PTA, dilutions are performed as needed, following the specific protocols and instrumental configurations. Participants for FFF-MALS, DLS/MADLS and PTA received 5 vials of TM to cover the sample need even when analyses with multiple techniques are performed (e.g. FFF-MALS+DLS, or DLS+PTA...). Thermoanalytical techniques required the entire 2 mL volume of a vial for a single measurement; in this case, participants received six vials: one for preliminary testing and five for replicate measurements.

Participants involved in the ILC using techniques for the size distribution measurements received a small amount (~200 µL) of polystyrene nanosphere™ size standard (Thermo Scientific, NIST traceable mean diameter) for quality control purposes. Quality Control Materials (QCM) were analysed according to the specific protocols; however, they are not part of the calibration process, and the associated results do not influence the inclusion or exclusion of participant data in the final ILC data treatment. Nonetheless, they may be considered during data evaluation to provide insights into participants' measurement capabilities (e.g., technical issues, potential bias, etc.).

Participants involved in the ILC using thermoanalytical techniques received a small amount of polypropylene powder (~1g) used for the preparation of the nano-PP samples (provided by BAM).

If other RMs or QCMs are included in the analysis, participants were encouraged to report details about their characteristics and to record the associated results in the electronic reporting form.

Upon reception, participants were asked (i) to keep the sample at ambient temperature and protected from light during storage, (ii) to not apply any treatment to the TM, QCM or their dilutions other than vortexing or bath sonication for up to 1 min.

Except for thermoanalytical techniques, sample preparation and analysis at room temperature was recommended. If the temperature at which the sample is analysed differs significantly from 20-25 °C, participants were asked to give details in the 'comments' section of the data reporting spreadsheet. It was recommended to control the temperature and monitor throughout the measurements. Therefore, instruments equipped with a temperature controller were recommended.

5. TECHNIQUES AND MEASURANDS

The measurement techniques addressed for this study and the principal measurands are summarised in Table 3. Secondary measurands may be indicated in the specific sections dedicated to each technique.

Table 3. Targeted measurement techniques and relative measurands

Measurement technique	Measurand
Light Scattering techniques (DLS, MADLS)	size distribution
Fractionation techniques hyphenated to Static Light Scattering (FFF-MALS)	size distribution
Particle Tracking Analysis (PTA)	number concentration
Thermoanalytical techniques (Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS)	mass fraction

The following sections did not intend to provide a standard operation procedure but guidance to participants on key aspects that could influence the comparability of results if not considered. Nonetheless, participants were encouraged to follow the proposed protocols and to report any deviations.

6. DLS/MADLS PROTOCOL

6.1. Sample Handling

The study sample can be measured neat providing low volume cuvette (e.g. ZEN2112 from Malvern Panalytical or equivalent) is available at the testing laboratory. If standard (i.e. ~1 ml volume) cuvette is used, sample dilution will be necessary to ensure enough volume is available for individual measurements. In case dilution is required, samples and diluent should be allowed to reach room temperature before the dilutions are performed. For dilutions, it is recommended to use ultrapure water, filtered (preferred pore size is 0.1 μm). If other diluent is used, details should be recorded in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended to dilute the study sample gravimetrically (i.e. using analytical balance to determine the mass of sample and diluent used, which allows calculation of the gravimetric dilution factor). The optimal dilution factor will vary depending on the instrumental set-up used.

6.2. Measurement protocol

It is recommended that the instrument is calibrated by the manufacturer and its performance is regularly verified by a qualified engineer. Please ensure that the type/model of the instrument, as well as software along with input parameter and data analysis mode (i.e. Cumulants or Distribution algorithms) are recorded in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended that the temperature is controlled and monitored throughout the measurements. Therefore, instruments equipped with a temperature controller are recommended.

It is generally recommended to switch on the instrument, at least 30 min before measurements, to ensure equilibrium conditions are reached. It is recommended to set the instrumental parameters (e.g. number of replicates, equilibration time, analysis mode, refractive index, density etc.) as considered best for the instrument's performance.

It is recommended to perform a blank measurement of the diluent before preparing the sample dilutions to test the purity of the diluent and help with data interpretation. It is also recommended that measurements of the blanks are repeated several times during each measurement session (batch, day etc.).

It is recommended to measure the particle size distribution in at least 3 vials of the study sample and record the obtained independent particle number concentration values per vial in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended to analyse 3 independent sample preparations/aliquots per vial and to record these results in the electronic reporting form. To ensure representative sampling, it is recommended to acquire at least 5 independent replicate measurements per each aliquot/preparation under the repeatability conditions (measurement repeats).

It is recommended to also measure RMs or QCs at the beginning and at the end of each measurement session (batch, day etc.) to monitor the instrument's performance. For the purpose of DLS/MADLS a sample of polystyrene quality control material has been provided by the study organisers. This sample should be diluted in ultrapure water prior to measurements gravimetrically and the dilution factor used should be recorded in the electronic reporting file. Participants are also welcomed to use other RMs/QCs of their choice and are encouraged to record relevant information in the electronic reporting form.

It is recommended to clean the cuvette with ultrapure water and dry between measurements of individual aliquots of the study material, blanks and RMs/QCs.

6.3. Data analysis

The participants should use their own *in-house* practice to decide which algorithm to use to derive size and size distribution from DLS/MADLS measurements and to calculate the associated measurement error. If measurement uncertainty cannot be calculated, standard deviation of the measurement can be reported instead (which should include the individual technical replicates (i.e. if each of the 3 preparations from each of 3 vials are measured 5 times under the repeatability conditions, the total number of individual values taken to calculate the mean and stdev is $n=45$).

Participants can attempt to estimate the uncertainty associated with the measurements following their own practice. In this case uncertainty should be recorded in the electronic reporting file in addition to standard deviation and details of the approach used to estimate it should also be recorded.

For example, parameters such as: within day variability in particle counting, between day variability in particle counting, input parameters (i.e. RI, density etc.) and method trueness can be considered as factors contributing to the overall measurement uncertainty. The uncertainty associated with method recovery can be estimated from measurements of RMs characterised for particle size, as:

$$\frac{\Delta R_m}{R_m} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta C_{meas}^{RM}}{d_{meas}^{RM}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta d_{RM}}{d_{RM}}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where d_{RM} is the nominal/given diameter of the RM and d_{meas}^{RM} is the RM diameter measured by DLS/MADLS.

Since no RM are being provided for this study, the participants who wish to perform such measurements are asked to identify suitable materials and record relevant information in the electronic reporting form.

Partners are requested to report average particle diameter from all individual measurements with associated measurement error and particle size distribution (as graph or histogram) representing average from all individual measurements.

6.4. Further reading

For more information on the DLS methods, we recommend ISO 22412:2017 'Particle size analysis — Dynamic light scattering (DLS)'.

7. FFF-MALS PROTOCOL

7.1. Overview

To complete the analysis, participants must have an instrument platform that includes the following detectors:

1. UV-Vis absorbance (single wavelength is sufficient)
2. Multi-angle light scattering (MALS)

Participants to FFF-MALS analyses receive:

- 1 vial of QCM that should be diluted in ultrapure water to an appropriate concentration according to the sensitivity of their detectors (e.g. 100 mg/L).
- 5 vials of TM: no dilution of the TM is required.

A new membrane is used at day 1 and conditioned by circulating the mobile phase overnight and by three injections/fractionations of the polystyrene QCM, followed by three direct injections of QCM for the recovery rate.

Each vial of TM should be analysed through three independent replicates of injections/fractionations performed on two different days (day 2 and day 3), resulting in a total of six measurements per sample. Additionally, three replicates of direct injections are performed daily for each sample to assess the recovery rate.

Blank injections are performed at the beginning and end of the analysis sequence. Wash injections are performed during the analysis sequence. Analyses are explained in detail in section 7.3.

Samples are fractionated using standard channel configurations, according to the parameters detailed in Table 4 below:

Table 4. MD-AF4 main parameters

Channel type	Standard channel
Membrane	Regenerated Cellulose 10 kDa
Spacer	350 µm or as close as possible
Mobile phase	Novachem or FL70; 0.0125%
Injected volume range	Proposed range: 10 - 50 µL; pick-up mode
Separation method	Power decay, provided in table format in the AF4-MALS Reporting File
λ_{max} UV (nm)	254 nm

The principal measurands for this study are particle size (radius of gyration in nm, also referred to as root mean square (RMS) radius) and analyte recovery (%). An Excel file for reporting is provided.

UV absorption should be monitored at 254 nm and will be used for recovery (R %) determination. The recovery is calculated as the ratio between the peak area of the fractionated peak ($A_{fractionated}$) to the peak area of the sample in simple injection without applying cross flow ($A_{unretained}$) (eq. 1):

$$R(\%) = \frac{A_{fractionated}}{A_{unretained}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

$A_{fractionated}$ is defined as the area of the retained peak, excluding the void peak and any peaks appearing after the crossflow reaches 0 mL·min⁻¹.

7.2. Instrumentation

Participants use commercial variants of the Wyatt Technology - Waters or Postnova Analytics AF4 instrumentation, equipped with the necessary pump(s), degasser, manual or auto injector, standard trapezoidal channel, and up-to-date software versions. Details about instrument setup/components and software version(s) should be reported in the reporting Excel file.

Set UV detector to 254 nm. The MALS detector should be calibrated and normalized according to manufacturer specifications or internal laboratory procedures.

Disable dilution control mode if available: channel flow rate = detector flow rate.

7.3. Mobile Phase Preparation

Participants prepare the mobile phase according to their laboratory procedure, using 0.1 µm filtered Type I purified water (i.e., resistivity at 25 °C ≥ 18 MΩ·cm).

7.4. Experimental Plan and Analysis Procedure

All elution parameters for fractionation, washing and recovery procedures are provided in table format in the **AF4-MALS Reporting File**. Find the appropriate tab labelled “**SOP-Wyatt**” or “**SOP-Postnova**”, depending on your AF4 system. Report any deviations from the defined elution programs using the tab for “**User Comments**”.

1. **DAY 1.** Begin with a new membrane. Insert the membrane and spacer and assemble the channel according to manufacturer instructions. If temperature control in the channel and/or MALS detector is available, set temperature to 25 °C. Otherwise, operate at ambient temperature. Ensure that the system is clean and conditioned for the study by circulating the mobile phase at least for 2 h prior to beginning analysis.
2. Inject an appropriate volume of QCM, according to the sensitivity of your detectors and following the elution program table “**Separation Method Parameters for Nano-PP**”. Perform three independent replicate injections/fractionations, followed by three direct injections of QCM for the recovery rate.
3. Ensure that the system is clean and conditioned for the study by circulating the mobile phase overnight.
4. **DAY 2.** Perform a blank injection of mobile phase following the elution program parameters used for the QCM/TM analysis and using the same injection volume.
5. Inject an appropriate volume of TM, according to the sensitivity of your detectors, in the range 10 to 50 µL and following the elution program table “**Separation Method Parameters for Nano-PP**”. Perform three independent replicate injections/fractionations, according to Table 3.
6. For each sample determine mass recovery by injecting the same amount of TM without the applied cross flow and without focusing step, according to the elution program table for “**Recovery Method Parameters for Nano-PP**” and Table 3.
7. Perform wash injections of mobile phase according to Table 3 and to “**Wash Method parameters for Nano-PP**” in the Excel file. The injection volume for the rinse step should meet or exceed that used for the TM.

8. Perform a blank injection of mobile phase at the end of the sequence following the elution program parameters used for the QCM/TM analysis and using the same injection volume.
9. Inject once more the QCM followed by a direct injection of QCM for the recovery rate to monitor the instrument's performance.
10. **DAY 3.** Repeat points 3 to 9.

Table 5 summarise the analysis sequence to enhance clarity.

Table 5. Analysis sequence. Nano-PP1 refers to nano-propylene vial 1 and so forth.

DAY 1 – Conditioning/QCM	DAY 2 – TM analysis/QCM	DAY 3 – TM analysis/QCM
Run	Run	Run
QCM 1	Blank 1	Blank 1
QCM 2	Nano-PP1 – replicate 1	Nano-PP1 – replicate 1
QCM 3	Nano-PP2 – replicate 1	Nano-PP2 – replicate 1
QCM recovery 1	Nano-PP3 – replicate 1	Nano-PP3 – replicate 1
QCM recovery 2	Nano-PP4 – replicate 1	Nano-PP4 – replicate 1
QCM recovery 3	Nano-PP5 – replicate 1	Nano-PP5 – replicate 1
	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 1	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 1
	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 1	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 1
	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 1	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 1
	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 1	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 1
	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 1	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 1
	Wash 1	Wash 1
	Nano-PP1 – replicate 2	Nano-PP1 – replicate 2
	Nano-PP2 – replicate 2	Nano-PP2 – replicate 2
	Nano-PP3 – replicate 2	Nano-PP3 – replicate 2
	Nano-PP4 – replicate 2	Nano-PP4 – replicate 2
	Nano-PP5 – replicate 2	Nano-PP5 – replicate 2
	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 2	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 2
	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 2	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 2
	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 2	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 2
	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 2	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 2
	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 2	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 2
	Wash 2	Wash 2
	Nano-PP1 – replicate 3	Nano-PP1 – replicate 3
	Nano-PP2 – replicate 3	Nano-PP2 – replicate 3
	Nano-PP3 – replicate 3	Nano-PP3 – replicate 3
	Nano-PP4 – replicate 3	Nano-PP4 – replicate 3
	Nano-PP5 – replicate 3	Nano-PP5 – replicate 3
	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 3	Nano-PP1_recovery – replicate 3

	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 3	Nano-PP2_recovery – replicate 3
	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 3	Nano-PP3_recovery – replicate 3
	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 3	Nano-PP4_recovery – replicate 3
	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 3	Nano-PP5_recovery – replicate 3
	Blank 2	Blank 2
	QCM 4	QCM 5
	QCM recovery 4	QCM recovery 5

7.5. Data treatment and reporting

Enter information about your instrumentation in the **Instrument tab** of the Excel reporting file. If you have both Wyatt and Postnova instruments and wish to participate in this study using both, please submit two separate copies of the Excel file, one for each system.

Participants are asked to **report the following parameters**:

- The **weight-average gyration radius, R_{gw}** , and the **$d10%$, $d50%$, and $d90%$ percentiles** of the size distribution calculated across the **FULL PEAK** for the TM. The participant define the region of interest based on his experience, realising a compromise between using the most of the peak and preserving the quality of the measured distribution. This involves considering R^2 values at the chromatographic peak extremities, where the signal-to-noise ratio decreases and the R_g distribution begins to scatter. The UV detector at 254 nm is used as concentration detector. Compared to the Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) approach, the data treatment using the FULL PEAK provides greater significance to weighted average results and allow comparability with batch methods.
- **The sample recovery (%)** determined according to section 7.1, for both the QCM and TM.
- Additionally, participant are also welcomed to report the **mean radius of gyration, \overline{R}_g** , for both QCM and TM. The radius of gyration should be calculated as the mean value of acquired data points averaged across the 90° LS peak at the FWHM. This data treatment ensure method comparability under strictly defined conditions.

MALS data treatment is performed as follows:

- Use Berry model first order.
- Inspect the angular data and determine which detectors to include in the fit, considering the R^2 values. We recommend selecting at least eight angles, including small angles whenever possible, as they play a crucial role in data processing.
- Whenever possible, the same set of angles, once determined, will be suitable for all the sample replicates.
- dn/dc value is not required to calculate the RMS radius, any non-zero value input for dn/dc will produce the same RMS value.

Reporting:

- Report the requested values in the **Results-TM tab** in the provided Excel file.
- Mass recovery is determined according to section 7.1: report UV peak areas (and volumes injected) in the **Results-TM tab** in the provided Excel file.
- Mean and standard deviation are automatically calculated using the reporting Excel file provided.
- Insert a graph showing the MALS scattering intensity at 90° as a function of elution time and the size distribution for the 30 replicate measurements and the respective blanks using the **Results-TM tab** in the provided Excel file. Size distributions should not be reported for blanks.

- Insert a graph showing the UV absorbance at 254 nm as a function of elution time for the 30 replicate measurements and the respective blanks using the [Results-TM tab](#) in the provided Excel file.

7.6. Further reading

For more information on the FFF method, we recommend ISO/TS 21362 'Nanotechnologies — Analysis of nano-objects using asymmetrical-flow and centrifugal field-flow fractionation'. According to ISO/TS 21362, the expected criterion to be fulfilled is a method recovery of $\geq 70\%$.

8. PTA PROTOCOL

8.1. Sample Handling

The study sample will require dilution before measurements. Samples and diluent should be allowed to reach room temperature before the dilutions are performed. For dilutions, it is recommended to use ultrapure water, filtered (preferred pore size is 0.1 μm). If other diluent is used, details should be recorded in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended to dilute the study sample gravimetrically (i.e. using analytical balance to determine the mass of sample and diluent used, which allows calculation of the gravimetric dilution factor), such that the final dilution aids in ~ 40 -60 particles per field of view. The optimal dilution factor will vary depending on the instrumental set-up used.

8.2. Measurement protocol

It is recommended that PTA is calibrated by the manufacturer and its performance is regularly verified by a qualified engineer. Instruments operating either in static or flow modes can be used for the measurements. Please ensure that the analysis mode, along with the type/model of the instrument, hardware and software are recorded in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended that the temperature is controlled and monitored throughout the measurements. Therefore, instruments equipped with a temperature controller are recommended

It is generally recommended to switch on the instrument, at least 30 min. before measurements, to ensure equilibrium conditions are reached. It is recommended to set the instrumental parameters (e.g. focus, camera levels, syringe pump flow, etc.) as considered best for the instrument's performance. It is important to clean the instrument's flow cell and tubing with ultrapure water and dry prior to measurements to ensure minimum background particle counts.

It is recommended to perform a blank measurement of the diluent before preparing the sample dilutions. If an unusually high particle number is detected (typically not more than 5 particles per field of view are expected) it is recommended that a flow cell and tubing are cleaned, and fresh diluent is prepared. The concentration of particles measured in the diluent can be taken into account when analysing sample data. Please note that for a fair assessment of the blank contribution, the diluent should be measured and analysed using the same instrument settings as used for the measurements of the study sample. It is also recommended that measurements of the blanks are repeated several times during each measurement session (batch, day etc.).

It is recommended to measure the particle number concentration in at least 3 vials of the study sample and record the obtained independent particle number concentration values per vial in the electronic reporting form. It is recommended to analyse 3 independent sample preparations per vial and to record these results in the electronic reporting form. To ensure representative sampling, it is recommended to acquire at least 5 independent videos of at least 60 s each per aliquot/preparation under the repeatability conditions (measurement repeats). The participants should use their own *in-house* practise to choose optimal sample dilution factor and report the results accounting for this dilution factor (i.e. the particle number concentration in the study sample)

It is recommended to also measure RMs or QCs at the beginning and at the end of each measurement session (batch, day etc.) to monitor the instrument's performance and to estimate the method recovery. Since no such materials are being provided for PTA for this study, the participants who wish to perform such measurements are asked to identify suitable materials and record relevant information in the electronic reporting form.

It is recommended to use ultrapure water to rinse between samples, blanks and RMs/QCs if used.

8.3. Data analysis

The participants should use their own *in-house* practice to calculate the number-based concentration of particles in the study sample and the associated measurement error. If measurement uncertainty cannot be calculated, standard deviation of the measurement can be reported instead (which should include the individual technical replicates (i.e. if each of the 3 preparations from each of 3 vials are measured 5 times under the repeatability conditions, the total number of individual values taken to calculate the mean and stdev is n=45). The particle number concentration C (g^{-1}) can be calculated as follows (*Note*: PTA usually provides particle number-based concentration in 'NP/ml', which can be converted to/reported as ' g^{-1} ' assuming diluent density of 1 g cm^{-3} , i.e. the conversion factor 1, is considered fit-for-purpose for this study):

$$C_{NP} = d_{PTA} \cdot C_{meas} \quad (1)$$

where C_{meas} is the average particle number concentration measured in the diluted sample and d_{PTA} is the gravimetric dilution factor.

Participants can attempt to estimate the uncertainty associated with the measurements following their own practice. In this case uncertainty should be recorded in the electronic reporting file in addition to standard deviation and details of the approach used to estimate it should also be recoded.

For example, parameters such as: within day variability in particle counting, between day variability in particle counting, dilution factor, particle detection threshold and method trueness can be considered as factors contributing to the overall measurement uncertainty. The uncertainty associated with the detection threshold, set by the user, can be estimated experimentally by varying this parameter over a reasonable range (input parameter, X axis) and looking at the effect this has on the measured particle number (measurement result, Y axis). The uncertainty associated with method recovery can be estimated from measurements of RMs characterised for particle number concentration, as:

$$\frac{\Delta R_m}{R_m} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta C_{meas}^{RM}}{C_{meas}^{RM}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta C_{RM}}{C_{RM}}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where C_{RM} is the nominal concentration of the RM and C_{meas}^{RM} is the RM concentration measured by PTA.

Since no RM are being provided for this study, the participants who wish to perform such measurements are asked to identify suitable materials and record relevant information in the electronic reporting form.

Except of particle number concentration, participants are also welcomed to report particle size (mean and modal diameters) and size distribution (as histogram or graph representing average from all individual measurements).

8.4. Further reading

For more information on the PTA method, we recommend ISO 19430:2024 'Determination of particle size distribution and number concentration by particle tracking analysis (PTA)'.

9. THERMOANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES PROTOCOL

The following instructions are not intended to serve as a standard operating procedure but rather as guidance for participants on key aspects that may affect the comparability of results if not taken into account. Participants are nonetheless encouraged to follow the proposed protocol and to report any deviations in the dedicated Excel reporting file.

This protocol specifically applies to py-GC/MS. Participants using TED-GC/MS are free to adapt the instructions as needed, in line with their internal laboratory procedures.

9.1 Sample preparation

Direct analysis is preferable to avoid particle loss and reduce blanks in the sample preparation step.

Samples are introduced into the Pyrolysis or TED unit directly into the pyrolysis cup or crucible:

- Transfer the entire contents of the nano-PP flask (2 ml) into the cup with a glass pipette. Refill the cup as the solvent evaporates.
- Rinse the flask with 200 μ L of Milli-Q water, repeating this step four times. Stir well to remove any residual particles that might remain in the flask.
- Rinse twice with 200 μ L of ethanol (EtOH), stirring to ensure complete transfer of all particles into the pyrolyser cup.
- Place the pyrolysis cup in an oven at 40 °C for at least 4 hours.

It is recommended to analyse the total volume of the nano-PP flask (2 mL), although the process is time-consuming. However, analysis of aliquots of the sample is also possible, in which case the volume analysed must be indicated in the report.

9.2 Instrumental conditions

Pyrolysis or thermal decomposition is carried out at temperature > 500 °C. When the sample is introduced, it is thermally decomposed into smaller and stable fragments. These pyrolysis and thermal products are then separated in a capillary GC column using the GC/MS operating conditions of your in-house validated procedure.

The instrumental conditions should be summarised in the Excel spreadsheet.

QA/QC measures should be implemented to prevent cross-contamination of the samples.

9.3 Calibration and quantification

Quantification is based on a calibration curve prepared using the micro-PP standard supplied by VAMAS. This standard should be analysed under the same conditions as the nano-PP sample.

The amount of polymer in the nano-PP sample is calculated using the concentrations of the marker compounds. Specific polypropylene (PP) pyrolysis products are integrated, with the most abundant and polymer-specific markers selected.

It is possible to use an Internal Standard (IS) if you have it included in your in-house validated procedure (e.g Anthracene-d10, Polystyrene-d8 or any other IS of your preference).

Other options, such as not using any IS, are also possible.

In any case, if an IS is used, it must be mentioned in the reporting sheet.

The following table shows the PP markers and their characteristic ions (m/z) used for identifying and quantifying nano-PP dispersed in water. Quantification is recommended using the 2,4-dimethylheptane as specific marker. Other markers can also be reported in the Excel spreadsheet.

Table 6. Polypropylene markers and their characteristic ions (m/z) which are used for the identification and quantification of nano-PP dispersed in water

Polymer	Characteristic Markers	Ion (m/z)
PP	<i>2,4-Dimethylhept-1-ene (recommended)</i>	70, 126
	2,4,6-trimethyl-1-nonene	69, 111
	2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene isotactic	69, 111
	2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene heterotactic	69, 111
	2,4,6,8-Tetramethyl-1-undecene syndiotactic	69, 111

10. PRELIMINARY FINDINGS OF VAMAS TWA 45, PROJECT 3

The ILC study is still ongoing, with some laboratories expected to finalise their measurements by the end of September 2025. A first evaluation of the performance of the four methods has been drafted: the results presented in the following tables show the percentage of data collected at the time of drafting this deliverable for each method. Standard statistical evaluation, in accordance with ISO 5725-2, has been applied by LNE to determine repeatability, reproducibility, and inter-laboratory variance for each measurement method.

10.1 Measuring size distribution by DLS/MADLS methods

To date, fourteen laboratories have participated in this ILC, and none were excluded from the initial data treatment. Preliminary results are presented in Figure 8 and Table 7, showing a repeatability of 5.2% and reproducibility of 7.7%.

Figure 8. Normalized nanoPP average size as characterised by DLS/MADLS methods.

Table 7. Preliminary evaluation of DLS/MADLS method performances. l_{exp} : expected final number of laboratories participating in the ILC for this technique; *Collected data*: percentage of data collected at the time of drafting this deliverable; l : number of participating laboratory; n : number of individual test results after outlier rejection; $o\%$: percentage of outliers; $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility; $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability; $C_{V,inter}$: coefficient of inter-laboratory variation.

l_{exp}	<i>Collected data</i>	l	n	$o\%$	$C_{V,R}$	$C_{V,r}$	$C_{V,inter}$	<i>Excluded labs</i>
18	72%	14	735	n.a.	7.7%	5.2%	5.7%	-

10.2 Measuring size distribution by FFF-MALS method

To date, five laboratories have participated in this ILC, and none were excluded from the initial data treatment. Preliminary results are presented in Figure 9 and Table 8, showing a repeatability around 3% and reproducibility in the 9-23% range in function of the parameter.

Figure 9. Normalised nanoPP average size as characterised by FFF-MALS method.

Table 8. Preliminary evaluation of FFF-MALS method performances. l_{exp} : expected final number of laboratories participating in the ILC for this technique; *Collected data*: percentage of data collected at the time of drafting this deliverable; l : number of participating laboratory; n : number of individual test results after outlier rejection; $o\%$: percentage of outliers; $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility; $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability; $C_{V,inter}$: coefficient of inter-laboratory variation.

(nm)	l_{exp}	Collected data	l	n	$o\%$	$C_{V,R}$	$C_{V,r}$	$C_{V,inter}$	Excluded labs
R_g (nm) - FWHM	12	50%	4	120	0.8	9%	2%	8%	-
R_{gw} - FP	12	50%	5	125	24	13%	3%	13%	-
d10% - FP	12	50%	5	125	24	23%	4%	22%	-
d50% - FP	12	50%	4	120	0.8	10%	3%	10%	-
d90% - FP	12	50%	4	120	25	17%	3%	17%	-

10.3 Measuring number concentration by PTA method

To date, eight laboratories have participated in this ILC, with one excluded from the initial data treatment. Preliminary results, presented in Figure 10 and Table 9, indicate a repeatability of 30% and a reproducibility of 60%.

Figure 10. Normalised nanoPP average size as characterised by PTA method.

Table 9. Preliminary evaluation of PTA method performances. I_{exp} : expected final number of laboratories participating in the ILC for this technique; *Collected data*: percentage of data collected at the time of drafting this deliverable; l : number of participating laboratory; n : number of individual test results after outlier rejection; $o\%$: percentage of outliers; $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility; $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability; $C_{V,inter}$: coefficient of inter-laboratory variation.

I_{exp}	<i>Collected data</i>	l	n	$o\%$	$C_{V,R}$	$C_{V,r}$	$C_{V,inter}$	<i>Excluded labs</i>
13	62%	7	315	28	60%	30%	52%	Lab. 18

10.4 Measuring mass fraction by thermoanalytical methods

To date, ten laboratories have participated in this ILC, with one excluded from the initial data treatment. Preliminary results, presented in Figure 11 and Table 10, indicate a repeatability of 32% and a reproducibility of 41%.

Figure 11. Normalised nanoPP mass fraction as characterised by thermoanalytical methods.

Table 10. Preliminary evaluation of thermoanalytical method performances. I_{exp} : expected final number of laboratories participating in the ILC for this technique; *Collected data*: percentage of data collected at the time of drafting this deliverable; I : number of participating laboratory; n : number of individual test results after outlier rejection; $o\%$: percentage of outliers; $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility; $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability; $C_{V,inter}$: coefficient of inter-laboratory variation.

I_{exp}	<i>Collected data</i>	I	n	$o\%$	$C_{V,R}$	$C_{V,r}$	$C_{V,inter}$	<i>Excluded labs</i>
12	75%	10	51	19.6	41%	32%	26%	Lab. 23

11. CONCLUSIONS

Preliminary findings of VAMAS TWA 45, Project 3, performed under the Plastic Trace project, show that size-based methods demonstrated good repeatability (2–5%) and reproducibility (8–23%), while mass fraction and number-based methods exhibited higher variability, with repeatability around 30% and reproducibility of 41% and 60% for pyrGC/MS and PTA, respectively. The NanoPP test material appears suitable as a reference material. However, the study must be completed with the missing participant results and subjected to thorough statistical analysis that considers sample preparation, instrumental details, and participant feedback. These results are preliminary and will be revised once all data have been received. They are planned to be first summarised in a VAMAS report, then published in an international peer-reviewed journal, and potentially incorporated into new ISO standards. The final datasets are also intended to be hosted in an open-access repository such as Zenodo. Overall, many valuable insights can be drawn from this collaborative exercise.

12. ANNEX I

Lactose Tablets as suitable Microplastics Reference Material to support validation studies and quality control

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ABSTRACT: Challenging for each method validation in the field of microplastics is the existence of suitable reference material describing the property of interest. The EU funded PlasticTrace project aims to overcome that gap by developing water-soluble tablets containing defined tiny particle numbers/masses of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (mass: 0.2, 18.5 and 400 μ g, particle number (Raman): 151 and 1764). Tablets are produced with solid phase dilution after a strict protocol with additional quality control. The PET particles used have a mean size of approx. 40 μ m ranging from 10 to 200 μ m and an irregular stone-like shape. All measurements were done following the ideas of ISO standardization body ISO/TC 147/SC 2/JWG 1 with the documents ISO/DIS 16094-2 and ISO/DIS 16094-3. The most accepted microplastics detection methods were used for homogenization measurements: μ -FTIR, μ -Raman, Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS. Different batches containing different particle numbers/masses going down to the limits of the methods were prepared and tested. The PET tablets show good tablet-to-tablet variation passing the homogeneity control (< 10%). They also show no changes within the first 6 month of storage. This reference material can help to fulfill the criteria of EU commission for monitoring of microplastics in drinking water and wastewater.

The increased awareness of the potential environmental and human health risks associated with microplastic (MP)

particles (1-1000 μ m, ISO/TR 21960:2020), combined with their ubiquitous occurrence globally, led to the precautionary

principle being applied by the European Union (EU) and to the first regulatory efforts. In recent years, multiple EU directives, such as the Drinking Water Directive (Directive (EU) 2020/2184) [1] and the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (Directive (EU) 2024/3019) [2], have made MP monitoring a mandatory requirement in an attempt to better understand MP transport pathways and their occurrence in water systems. Based on the understanding achieved by such monitoring, an effective reduction of MP contamination of such water systems and the wider environment is possible by targeted regulation.

However, regulation needs standards and these standards need validated, harmonized analysis techniques, including sampling, sample preparation and detection. Furthermore, the development and validation of standard methods requires reference materials that are fit for that specific purpose, and which fulfill the criteria needed. For example, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) body ISO/TC 147/SC 2/JWG 1 recently published the standards ISO/DIS 16094-2 [3] for number-based spectroscopy detection and quantification of MP in water, and ISO/DIS 16094-3 [4] for mass-based thermo-analytical identification and quantification of MP in water. The most commonly used spectroscopy methods for identifying and quantifying the number of MP counting particles are micro Fourier–transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR) or micro Raman spectroscopy (μ -Raman), which both use a combination of microscope imaging for particle counting and size determination and spectroscopy for polymer identification. Similarly, the most used thermo-analytical techniques for quantifying the mass of polymer particles present in a sample are pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) and thermal extraction desorption-GC-MS (TED-GC/MS).

Many scientific questions can be answered by usage of well-characterized test materials, but these are often bespoke materials produced for a specific purpose or application. In the case of standards, however, it is important to prove the quality of a test material according to physicochemical properties, contamination, homogeneity and stability. Following the idea of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), a research-grade test material must be well-characterized. A reference material is proven to be homogeneous and stable in one property of interest, whereas with a certified reference material the measured variable should also be traceable to the SI units [5]. As any MP reference material must be usable for the monitoring of MP in a range of matrices, it must very closely reflect the real MP particles found in the environment or in consumer products. This means, the particles should be primarily irregular-shaped fragments with sharp edges, mainly in the size range of 10-100 μ m. The concentration of MP in a reference material sample should reflect that expected in relevant environmental matrices to ensure appropriate method validation. As higher MP concentrations are typically found in environmental samples (e.g. wastewater) and lower

concentrations are found in food products or biota, reference material samples should be produced at different concentrations to cover these different needs. In general, MP reference material samples should have total masses that are in μ g range, which is difficult to achieve even with analytical balances. Furthermore, these very low masses need to be transported quantitatively, ensuring all end users are working with comparable samples. These challenges can be overcome by tableting. In principle, all MP particles can be embedded with tableting irrespective of their shape and polymer type. For most polymer types, MP particles <100 μ m can be readily produced by cryo-milling a polymer granulate feedstock material, sometimes with the application of further fragmentation techniques, and applying subsequent sieving to achieve the desired particle size range for the planned reference material [6,7,8,9].

The aim of this study was to produce a reference material that would support standardization and regulation of MP and could be used for in-house method validation to increase accuracy and precision as quality control, as well as increasing lab-to-lab harmonization processes. A quality-by-design (QbD) [10,11] approach was applied to fulfill the criteria on a well-characterized reference material. Tablets were pressed containing polyethylene terephthalate (PET) with a size range of 10-100 μ m with sharp edges and an irregular morphology.

The overall mass included in the tablets was varied to achieve three different concentrations: (1) an environmental-like concentration for mass-based thermo-analytical methods, (2) a food-related concentration that was detectable for both mass- and number-based analysis methods, and (3) a very low mass approaching the limit of reporting (LOR) for number-based spectroscopic methods [3]. The MP particles (starting material) were characterized for size and shape with laser diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), while polymer verification was conducted by FTIR. To produce a viable reference material for the mass-based method concentrations, homogeneity and stability control assessment was completed with at least 10 individual tablets using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) according to ISO Guide 30 [12] and ISO 33405:2024 [13]. The tablets containing the lowest PET MP concentration was homogeneity and stability checked with μ -FTIR and μ -Raman. The full scheme of analysis can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Production process and characterization methods used for the different batches (Batch 1: B1, Batch 2: B2, Batch 3: B3) of tablets containing the different PET MP concentrations and for Blanks containing the tablet matrix only.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Lactose (MEGGLE GmbH & Co. KG), polyethylene glycol 6000 (PEG, Merck), PET (BAM) and Low-density polyethylene (LDPE, Schaetti AG, Wallisellen) were used. More details can be found in the Supplementary Information.

Tableting PET and PE MP test materials. To circumvent the difficulties associated with the weighing of very small masses and their quantitative transportation, the MP particles were embedded in lactose and a lubricant (PEG). Tablets were pressed with a conventional tablet press used for producing pharmaceutical tablets. Lactose is commonly used in pharmaceutical applications as a cost-effective matrix for ingredients or drugs. It is easy to handle in the laboratory, can be readily produced under clean conditions, and can be directly pressed without transport packaging contamination in the final product, when often plastics is used for packaging. Furthermore, the resulting tablets are both water-soluble and non-toxic, making them easy to use in the laboratory. To produce the tablets, the water-soluble lactose, PET particle test material and PEG were mixed together with in equal amounts. The PEG is added to act as a lubricant during the tablet pressing process. The first batch of tablets (Batch 1) started with 1.05 g of each of the three ingredients being mixed together with a tumble mixer (LM-TM100, Laarmann, Roermond, Netherlands) for 10 mins (Table 1). After this time, an additional 10.5 g of lactose and PEG were added to the sample to make the first dilution step and a further 10 min of mixing applied. Subsequent dilutions of the PET with additional lactose and PEG are outlined in Table 1, with mixing applied at each dilution step. Once the final dilution and mixing step (20 min) had been completed, resulting in a PET concentration of 2.2

mg/g, small aliquots of the mixed powder were pressed into tablets using a TDP 5 Desktop Tablet Press (LFA Tablet Press, Bicester, United Kingdom). The stainless-steel punch had a diameter of 8 mm. Each tablet has a mass of 250 +/- 5 mg. An additional two batches of tablets (Batch 2 and Batch 3) were produced using the same dilution and mixing procedure as described for Batch 1, but with starting amounts of PET test material of 0.03 and 0.01 g, respectively. Finally, a batch of blank tablets was produced according to the same method, but without the addition of PET particles.

Table 1. Sample preparation procedure for PET Batch 1 tablets (Batch 2 and 3 in brackets)

	Tablet ingredients			PET Concentration (mg/g of matrix)	Mixing time (min)
	PET (g)	Lactose (g)	PEG (g)		
Batch 1 (Batch 2/3)	1.05 (0.03/0.01)	1.05	1.05	333 (14.1/4.7)	10
1 st dilution step	-	10.5	10.5	43.5 (1.3/0.4)	10
2 nd dilution step	-	19.2	19.2	16.8 (0.48/0.16)	10
3 rd dilution step	-	38.5	-	10.4 (0.3/0.1)	10
4 th dilution step	-	115.5	-	4.8 (0.14/0.05)	10
5 th dilution step	-	255.1	-	2.2 (0.06/0.02)	20

Owing to the different starting amounts of PET test material added to the mixture in each of the batches, the resulting tablets contained different particle numbers/masses. This provided a range of reference materials that were suitable for assessing the detection limits of the individual thermo-analytical and spectroscopic analysis techniques. The different batches contain various theoretical masses of PET per tablet as follows:

- Batch 1: 400 μg
- Batch 2: 18.5 μg
- Batch 3: 0.2 μg
- Blanks: 0 μg (matrix only)

A total of 1000 tablets were pressed from each of the Batch 1 and Batch 2 mixtures, while 200 tablets were prepared from the Batch 3 mixture and 200 tablets were prepared from the blank matrix mixture. At least 20% of all tablets in each batch were weighed gravimetrically (Mettler Toledo AT DeltaRange® analytical balance). All tablets that exceeded the weight range of 250 ± 5 mg were considered to be outside of the acceptable tolerance range and were discarded.

Quality by design approach. QbD is a well-established concept within the pharmaceutical industry. Essentially, it is an approach for manufacturing products in such a way that they serve a specific purpose. This requires targeted production processes to reach specific quality target product profiles for the final product [10,11]. The product is therefore designed specifically for the purpose for which it is intended to be used later. To apply the QbD approach to the field of microplastics, a range of parameters must be tested and verified for the reference material to be considered suitable for the validation of the thermo-analytical and spectroscopic detection methods (Table 2). These parameters were used for characterisation of the PET particles and define the analytical detection methods. A detailed description of the methods is presented in the Supplementary Information.

Table 2. Parameters following the QbD approach for a reference material for validation of detection methods

	Measurand	Methods
Homogeneity and stability control (monitored parameter)	Mass fraction	TGA
Characterized concentration values	Particle number	μ -FTIR, μ -Raman
	Mass fraction	Py-GC/MS, TED-GC/MS
Identification and dimensional characterization	Size and size distribution	Laser diffraction
	Shape	SEM
	Polymer type	FTIR

Processing of tablets for PET analysis. Sample preparation involves dissolution and filtration of the tablet to isolate the PET reference material, where the filtration is carried out according to a jointly developed standard operating procedure [14]. The MilliQ water required for dissolution is provided in-house at each user laboratory but should always be filtered through a 200 nm filter prior to use. Si filters used are produced by chemical etching (Smart membranes, Germany) with 5 μ m round pores (Fig. S1, left). The pitch of the filters is 12 μ m, the depth 270 μ m and the roughness of the top surface of the filter is about 10 nm. The filters are cut by laser dicing to the desired diameter of 9 mm. The Si filters are reusable and can be cleaned

by washing with ethanol and acetone in an ultrasonic bath. Each filtration unit was validated in-house prior to use with the PET tablets. To enable more efficient filtration and analysis by the thermo-analytical instruments, dedicated filter-crucibles for TGA and TED-GC/MS measurements were designed (Fig. S1, right). The filter-crucible (GKD - Gebr. Kufferath AG, Düren, Germany) has a height of 13 mm and a diameter of 9 mm. The filter material is welded at the bottom to prevent particle loss during filtration [15].

Homogeneity and stability control studies. The homogeneity of the PET tablets was assessed by a total of 10 tablets from each of Batch 1 and Batch 2 that were filtered over a 5 μ m pore sized filter (stainless steel, 9 mm in diameter) and analyzed by TGA to determine the mass of PET polymer in each individual tablet. A small mass loss between 25 and 200 °C typically indicates the loss of any water present in the sample, while biological compounds decompose at higher temperatures. The mass loss of polymers typically occurs at between 350 and 500°C. Although individual polymer types can give different DTGs, TGA and similar methods are not feasible for identifying different polymer types within one sample, nor for distinguishing their quantitative mass loss as the decomposition temperature areas can interfere with each other. TGA only works effectively for simple systems/mixtures where all compounds or components are known, and the individual DTGs are sufficiently far away from each other. Stability control was performed on Batch 1 and Batch 2 tablets after 6 and 12 months, respectively.

Quality assurance/quality control. All labs followed the ISO 16094-2 and 16094-3 norms [3, 4] regarding quality assurance and quality control, including the management of reagents, taking relevant precautions with laboratory environment, and the use of analytical control blanks. Careful attention was given to ensuring all the reagents used in the sample/filtration process, including the reference water and chemicals (ethanol, surfactant), were pre-filtered before use with a non-polymeric membrane with a pore size ≤ 5 μ m to remove any contaminant microplastics. The ubiquitous nature of microplastic in the working environment was considered by taking contamination prevention measures, including not wearing gloves, washing hands and washing the outside of all containers. Laboratory personnel wore cotton lab coats and did not wear face masks or cosmetics. Most work was conducted under a laminar flow hood that was regularly cleaned. The use of plastic-based equipment was avoided to prevent cross-contamination.

The establishment of analytical control blanks is mandatory to measure the impact of the different steps (sampling and filtration) and ensure the quality and significance of the analysis is in line with ISO standard 12141:2024 [16]. For that purpose, an analytical control blank comprising particle-free water of known quality was produced for each analysis in series. This

blank followed the same protocol as the corresponding sample and was analyzed first to ensure that no contamination has been introduced during the sampling and filtration process. This is most important for number-based quantification methods, which detect each individual particle. Although the same blank controls were used for mass-based quantification methods, the mass of any possible contamination is often below the LOD. The number or mass of PET particles found in the blank samples were subtracted from the results of the main samples as part of accurate measurements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2: SEM image (left) and particle size distribution of PET particles (right).

Characterization of PET particles. The PET polymer type was confirmed by ATR-FTIR measurements of the pristine PET powder (Fig. S2). SEM images showed that the pristine PET particles were irregular shaped with sharp edges, and that a range of particle sizes was evident (Fig. 2). Laser diffraction analysis confirmed that the pristine PET particles had a broad size distribution, with distribution density values of $D_{10}=19.1 \pm 0.2$ (1.0%), $D_{50}=42.4 \pm 0.2$ (0.4%) and $D_{90}=72.9 \pm 0.3$ (0.5%), where $D_{10}/D_{50}/D_{90}$ is the equivalent particle diameter of the measured volume below which 10.3/50.3/90.3% of the particles are. It should be noted that 93.5% of all particles are in the size range between 20 and 100 μm with an approximately equal number distributed across the size fractions 20-50 μm (49.1%) and 50-100 μm (44.4%) (Table 3).

Homogeneity and stability control studies. The PET tablets consist of three components, which TGA of each component revealed that they exhibited different DTGs: lactose (DTG = 301.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), PEG (DTG = 361.7 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and PET (DTG = 430.9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Fig. 3) [17]. The DTG is the peak maxima of the first time derivative of the mass loss curve determined in TGA. The mass loss rate curves indicated that there is a slight interference between the mass loss of PEG and PET between 330 and 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Since PEG is easily soluble in water and should therefore no longer be present on the filter after filtration process is completed and the PET particles have been isolated, it is assumed that the total mass loss observed in the temperature

range 330-480 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ represents only PET and gives a direct mass correlation ($m(\text{mass loss}, 330-480 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}) = m(\text{PET in tablet})$).

Figure 3: Mass loss (left) and mass loss rate (right) of lactose, PEG and PET of TGA measurements.

The first indication of PET homogeneity in the tablets is presented in Fig. 4 (see Table S1 and S2). Lactose and PEG decompose at lower temperatures than PET during the heating. Furthermore, both the lactose and the PEG should have been fully dissolved and removed during the filtration step, and the mass loss between 330 and 480 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ can be assumed to represent the mass of PET lost. The theoretical PET mass of 400 μg (Batch 1) and 18.6 μg (Batch 2) matches well with the calculated mean masses ($n=10$) by TGA measurements, where $m(\text{Batch 1}) = 398.0 \pm 47.3 \mu\text{g}$ and $m(\text{Batch 2}) = 19.6 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{g}$. The standard deviation for both Batches is approx. 8-12%. It should be noted that the uncertainty of the TGA itself is 2 μg according to the manufacturer.

Figure 4: PET masses per tablet determined by TGA for Batch 1 (left) and Batch 2 (right) as a homogeneity control; $n=10$.

Mass-based thermo-analytical methods. The reference material must be known for validation of microplastic detection methods. In accordance with the QbD approach implemented in the current study and the ISO document ISO/DIS 16094-3, other mass-based methods were used to measure the amount of PET present in the Batch 1 and Batch 2 tablets to provide supporting information to the TGA as a basis for conducting the homogeneity control and to give reference values for the selected mass-based detection methods. A total of 17 PET-containing tablets from Batch 1 were each analyzed with Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS with direct sample preparation (PET tablet particles on filters). Further measurements were carried

out with 10 tablets that were analyzed by Py-GC/MS after derivatization of the PET particles (Fig. 5, see Table S1 and S2). Batch 3 PET tablet results according to mass were not shown but are detected by one lab with $0.27 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g}$ (RSD: 19.7%, $n=10$).

All 44 measurements of Batch 1 are in good relation to each other, with a mean mass value of $422.3 \mu\text{g}$, a mean standard deviation (STD) of $88.7 \mu\text{g}$, and a mean relative STD 21.0%. Importantly, this mean PET mass value is fully consistent with the reference value of $398.0 \pm 47.3 \mu\text{g}$ determined in the homogeneity control by TGA. Direct Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS show quite comparable mean values of $448.9 \mu\text{g}$ and $431.3 \mu\text{g}$, respectively, with both slightly overestimating the mass of PET relative to the TGA reference value. The STD of TED-GC/MS ($55.7 \mu\text{g}$) is lower than that of Py-GC/MS ($105.1 \mu\text{g}$). The derivatized PET particles detected by Py-GC/MS gave a slight underestimation compared to the reference value, indicating not all of the PET particles were fully derivatized. Non-derivatized PET will not be detected when using dimethyl terephthalate as the quantifier.

Figure 5: PET masses per tablet detected with direct Py-GC/MS analysis, direct TED-GC/MS analysis, and with derivatization Py-GC/MS analysis. The table gives mean values, STD and relative STD in numbers. The results for Batch 1 PET tablets are presented on the left side of the figure and the results for Batch 2 PET tablets are presented on the right side of the figure.

The concentration of PET particles in the Batch 2 tablets is diluted by a factor of 30 compared to the Batch 1 tablets. This dilution was conducted to achieve a PET concentration that is more realistic according to the microplastic mass/numbers found in food products. For Batch 2, 10 tablets were directly analyzed by Py-GC/MS and 10 tablets were directly analyzed by TED-GC/MS. A further 10 tablets were analyzed by Py-GC/MS using derivatization. All three methods show similar mean values with an average of $17.1 \pm 5.7 \mu\text{g}$ (33.1%) that corresponds well to the TGA reference value of $19.8 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{g}$. The direct and derivatized Py-GC/MS measurements are very similar in mass (17.7 and $16.8 \mu\text{g}$) and STD (3.9 and $4.5 \mu\text{g}$), while the STD and relative STD of the TED-GC/MS

measurements is quite high with values of $8.2 \mu\text{g}$ and 48.6% , respectively.

The Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS analyses show generally the same masses for both Batch 1 and Batch 2 tablets as those determined by TGA. The higher PET masses present in the Batch 1 tablets are slightly overestimated compared to the TGA, while the smaller PET masses in the Batch 2 tablets, which are near the instrumental LODs, are within the TGA reference value or are slightly underestimated. Overall, the masses and the STDs are in the same range for both batches of PET tablets and correspond well with theoretical values and the TGA reference values. This makes the PET tablets a valuable product for use in method validation for microplastic identification and quantification methods supporting EU directives and monitoring campaigns to measure true values.

Figure 6: PET masses per tablet determined by mass-based methods for Batch 1 (left) and Batch 2 (right) as stability control assessment; $n=2-5$ (The red line indicates the theoretical mass).

Stability control of the PET tablets was performed on 2 to 5 tablets after 6 months for Batch 1 and after 12 months for Batch 2 (Fig. 6, see Table S7, S8 and S9). No significant changes in mass could be observed for either batch of tablets using TGA, Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS relative to the values determined at month 0. These results indicate that the PET tablets, irrespective of the PET concentration, are stable over these timeframes.

Spectroscopic methods. The PET-containing tablets were also analyzed for particle numbers and size distributions as this is an important metric for supplementing the mass, especially as microplastic monitoring typically requires particle number to be reported. The Batch 1 tablets was not analyzed using the spectroscopic techniques as the high concentration of PET particles would result in too many particles being collected on the filters. This has the double challenge of overloading the filters and making it difficult for the image-based techniques to identify and analyze individual particles, while a higher number of particles requires much more time to complete a full analysis of the filter. Therefore, the Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets with a

lower theoretical PET particle concentration were analyzed with the spectroscopic techniques.

Figure 7: Lab-to-lab comparison of PET particle numbers per tablet detected by μ -Raman of three different partner for Batch 2.

Three different laboratories measured the Batch 2 tablets to determine the number of PET particles numbers and their respective sizes. One lab analyzed 8 tablets (Lab 2) with μ -Raman, another lab analyzed 10 tablets with μ -Raman (Lab 3), and the final lab analyzed 10 tablets with μ -Raman and μ -FTIR (Lab 1). A comparison of the resulting PET tablet particle numbers, which are counted and sorted for the size fractions 1-5, 5-10, 10-20, 20-50, 50-100 and 100-500 μm , is shown in Fig. 7 (see Table S3). In addition, the values are compared to those determined by laser diffraction for the pristine PET particles. The particle numbers in the individual size classes match well within and between the laboratories. The mean total particle number ($n=28$) in the Batch 2 tablets with a size between 20 and 500 μm is 1,764 \pm 155 (8.8%). The sizes correspond well with the results of the laser diffraction.

Table 3: Comparison of integrated areas of distinct size fractions determined with laser diffraction to mean values of all partners of particle numbers per fraction and over all 28 tablets measured.

		Size fraction	μm	5-10	10-20	20-50	50-100	100-500
Laser diffraction	Ratio		%	0.5	4.4	49.1	44.4	1.7
	integrated area							
μ -Raman	Ratio		%	9.3	19.0	49.7	18.8	3.2
	integrated area (mean all labs)							

A direct comparison of the relative number of particles per size class determined by μ -Raman and the integrated area of the size

classes determined by laser diffraction shows relatively good agreement (Table 3). Almost 50% of all particles were in the size range of 20-50 μm . A shift towards detecting a higher proportion of smaller particles could be observed for μ -Raman. It could be evidence that the tableting process is fragmenting the particles leading to an increase in smaller particles and a decrease in the larger particle size fractions. It is also known that laser diffraction can be evaluated according to the Fraunhofer or the MIEE model, which are more suitable for larger or smaller particles. As the size distribution is broad, the Fraunhofer evaluation was used as a compromise, with larger particles being preferred.

While laser diffraction showed that 44% of PET particles were in the size range 50-100 μm , the number of particles counted with μ -Raman in this size class represented only 19%. Furthermore, μ -Raman detected higher proportions of PET particles in the smaller size classes 10-20 and 5-10 μm .

Figure 8: Comparison of particle numbers of Batch 2 (left) and Batch 3 (right) detected with μ -FTIR and μ -Raman, $n=10$, all measurements are done in the same laboratory (Lab 1).

The particle number counted with μ -Raman for Batch 2 were also compared to particle number values determined with μ -FTIR. The particle size detection limit for μ -FTIR is larger than detection limit for μ -Raman. According to ISO/DIS 16094-2, therefore, μ -FTIR analysis was only performed for particles larger than 20 μm . A similar comparison was conducted for the Batch 3 tablets containing the lowest concentration of PET particles. The results are presented in Fig. 8 (see Table S3, S4 and S5). Although the total number of particles has been reduced from 1759 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) for Batch 2 to 151 particles for Batch 3 ($n=10$, μ -Raman, 5-500 μm) it is clear that the size distribution is similar. The particle numbers counted with μ -Raman and μ -FTIR for both Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets were similar for particle sizes larger than 50 μm . In contrast, μ -FTIR detects 56% less (Batch 2) and 55% less

(Batch 3) PET particles than μ -Raman in the 20-50 μm size category. The similar size distribution independent of the concentration, indicates a systematic measurement error based on different measurement methods [16].

For the μ -Raman, all size distributions for Batch 2 and Batch 3 tablets determined by microscopy show the highest relative standard deviations for smallest and largest size categories (5-10 and 100-500 μm), while the lowest relative standard deviations were recorded for the size fraction 20-50 μm . This is probably due to the number of particles per size class. From a statistical point of view, it is easier to distribute more particles of the same size homogeneously from tablet to tablet than fewer particles. The presence or absence of individual particles in a tablet changes the relative standard deviation much more when the total number of particles in a size class is very small. For the μ -FTIR data the relative standard deviations are notably higher across all measured size categories compared to the equivalent μ -Raman values. The highest relative standard deviations for both Batch 2 and Batch 3 are observed for the smallest size category measurable by μ -FTIR (20-50 μm). This indicates that particles in this size range, at least those around 20 μm , are at the instrumental limits of detection, as μ Raman analysis consistently showed that the 20-50 μm size range contained the highest number of PET particles in all tablets tested. The results clearly demonstrate that μ -FTIR can robustly determine PET particle numbers down to a particle size of 50 μm , while μ -Raman allows robust identification and quantification of PET particles down to at least 20 μm .

Matrix contamination. Although blank control samples need to be conducted for determination of accurate particle mass and number measurements as part of QA/QC, it is equally important to analyze the matrix (lactose and PEG) as possible source for contamination. Therefore, matrix blank tablets were produced containing lactose and PEG but with no addition of PET particles. These tablets were tested in the participating different laboratories for particle number and mass after running through the entire filtration process in the same way as for the PET-containing tablets. Analysis of the resulting data revealed that no thermoplastic polymers were detected in the matrix material using thermo-analytical methods. This indicates that no thermoplastic particles were present or, more likely, that the mass of any polymer contamination is below the LODs of the instruments.

In contrast to the thermo-analytical analysis of the matrix blank tablets, six different types of polymer particle were detected in the number-based spectroscopic approaches. A summary of the results is provided in Fig. 9. Polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), PET, polyamide (PA) and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) particles were found across 8 tablets analyzed by μ -Raman and 7 tablets analyzed by μ -FTIR. For μ -Raman, 6 of the 8 matrix blank tablets contained polymer

particles, ranging in number from 1 particle to 51 particles. PS particles dominate 3 of the tablets (27-32 particles), while PET (1-6 particles) was found in 5 of the matrix blank tablets. For μ -FTIR, all 7 of the matrix blank tablets contained polymer particles, ranging in number from 2 particles to 36 particles. PET particles were found in 5 of the 7 the matrix blank tablets, ranging from 1-16 particles.

Figure 9: Plastic contamination found in matrix blank tablets as determined by μ -Raman and μ -FTIR ($n=8/n=7$).

Overall, the number of contaminant particles detected was very low (>3%) compared to the total mean number of PET particles present in the Batch 2 tablets (1,759 particles). In the case of the Batch 2 tablets, the matrix is considered to be sufficiently clean for it to be used to produce reference materials containing this concentration of PET particles. It should be noted that the number of polymer particles identified by the spectroscopic methods in the matrix blank tablets includes both matrix contamination as well as any possible contamination occurring during the sample production, storage, transportation, sample preparation (filtration) and measurement of the filter itself. When comparing the two analysis techniques, μ -Raman detects more particles than μ -FTIR. This is expected due the lower particle size detection limit of Raman microscopes and may explain why PS particles were not found in μ -FTIR if they are smaller than 20 μm . PTFE particle contamination was also only be detected by μ -Raman, which indicates that the particles are again <20 μm and that somewhere in the sample preparation process a seal made of PTFE was used. It should also be noted that PS and PTFE contamination was only found in the same 3 tablets analyzed by μ -Raman and not the other 5 tablets, indicating the contamination was not consistent.

Tablets with smaller particle sizes and LDPE as Outlook. Recognizing that tablet production works very well for the PET particles utilized in the current study and knowing that reference

materials comprising more polymer types are needed to monitor microplastics, we tried to press commercially available LDPE particles into ‘Batch 2’ type tablets with the same lactose and PEG matrix (see Table S10). These particles proved to be much more challenging than the PET particles due to the mean particle size being D50: 18.0 +/- 0.7 μm . This size distribution mainly covers the most challenging region of <50 μm for the number-based $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ and $\mu\text{-Raman}$ spectroscopic methods. The homogeneity control determined by TGA showed a mean LDPE mass of 17.8 +/- 1.6 μg , which perfectly matches the theoretical mass (17.9 μg) (Fig. S3, Table S11).

Lab 1 and Lab 3 determined the total particle number by $\mu\text{-Raman}$ with mean total numbers of LDPE particles being 6205 +/- 469 and 5460 +/- 1069, respectively (Fig. S4, Table S12, S13 and S14). As with the PET tablets, the mean total number of LDPE particles detected by $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ (1589 +/- 206, Lab 1) was lower compared to $\mu\text{-Raman}$. This result is expected given the small average size of the LDPE particles (18 μm) incorporated into the tablets. As a result, a high proportion of the LDPE particles are below the LOR for $\mu\text{-FTIR}$. The total particle number determined by $\mu\text{-Raman}$ differs for the smallest size category (5-10 μm) between Lab 1 and Lab 3. Similarly large differences between the total particle numbers derived by the two laboratories are observed for the 20-50 μm and the 100-500 μm size categories. As one lab is not consistently reporting higher particle numbers across all size categories further investigation is needed into why this is the case.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

Supporting Information contains detailed information on measurement procedures for the individual analytical techniques as well as tables with the individual PET or LDPE particle numbers and masses determined for homogeneity and stability control. The dilution scheme of LDPE production is also presented.

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KA: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – original draft, YW: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, PF: Investigation, CW: Investigation, CD: Writing – review & editing, UB: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, MF: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, MP: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, AS: Investigation, AMR: Funding acquisition, Supervision, SML: Supervision, Writing – review & editing, CMP: Investigation, VFG: Investigation, PTM:

Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, NB: Supervision, Writing – review & editing, LC: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, AM: Investigation, BvB: Conceptualization, VKS: Conceptualization, AB: Supervision, Writing – review & editing, LS: Investigation, EA: Supervision, CCJ: Investigation, Writing – review & editing, AMG: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision

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13. ANNEX II

Micro and Nano Plastics in the Environment Technical Working Area 45

Call for Participation

Project 3

An interlaboratory comparison on candidate reference materials to support the standardization of nanoplastic analysis

Objectives

To validate method performance for targeted techniques that measure the size distribution, number concentration and mass fraction of nanoplastic particles.

Measurement Techniques

Size distribution:

- Light Scattering methods including versions hyphenated to fractionation (DLS, MADLS, FFF-MALS)

Number Concentration:

- Particle Tracking Analysis (PTA)

Mass Fraction:

- Thermoanalytical techniques (Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS)

Results will support harmonization and pre-standardization, providing data for assessing method repeatability and reproducibility.

Background

Several research needs have been identified by International Organizations as the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA), the Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA), and the World Health Organization (WHO). Among these is the development of representative reference materials for plastic particles across various size ranges.

As part of the EURAMET Plastics Trace Project (<https://plastictrace.eu/>) sub-micron plastic particles and nanoplastics, reflective of common industrial polymers, have been produced and characterized. However, standardized measurement protocols and methodologies for the reliable analysis of the physico-chemical properties of nanoplastics are still absent. For the validation of methods, instrumentation and parameters for nanoplastics, this interlaboratory comparison (ILC) is being organized to evaluate the performance of targeted techniques to measure the size distribution, number concentration and mass fraction of nanoplastic particles.

Standardization needs

- There is a critical need for validated and standardized protocols for nanoplastics characterization.
- Results from this ILC aim to contribute to new documentary standards in ISO.

Work Programme

- Surfactant-free aqueous suspensions of nano-polypropylene test materials will be distributed in February 2025.
- A minimum of five measurement replicates is demanded.

Figures: Morphology of nano-polypropylene test material captured via electron microscopy imaging (left); (Right) a photograph of the surfactant-free aqueous suspension sample.

- Participants will receive SOPs for sample preparation, measurement, and data analysis.
- The time required to carry out the measurements may depend on the technique; 1 week is a rough estimate.
- All participants are asked to return data and other requested information (e.g., quality control details, technical issues encountered, etc.) using the data reporting templates provided by the study organizers.
- Measurement results will be statistically evaluated for repeatability and reproducibility using ISO 5725-2.

Status: The project will start in February 2025 for a duration of 6 months.

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Register your interest

www.vamas.org
January 2025

Deliverables and Dissemination

This interlaboratory study will be summarized in a VAMAS report, and disseminated at scientific conferences, and in a peer-reviewed scientific journal. Data produced in this ILC may contribute to assignment of reference values to the test material.

Funding: Participants fund their own involvement in the project.